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AUTHORS

Melike Taskiran
<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6324-9229>

Halit Canberk Aydoğan
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7861-4297>

Hacer Yasar Teke
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2311-5145>

AFFILIATIONS

Department of Forensic Medicine
Ordu University Training and Research Hospital
Ordu, Turkey

Department of Forensic Medicine
Ordu University Training and Research Hospital
Ordu, Turkey

Department of Forensic Medicine
Ordu University Training and Research Hospital
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Community Health Centers (CHCs) and Family Health Centers (FHCs) serve as primary forensic evaluation points, issuing preliminary forensic reports (Bozkurt et al., 2015). The accuracy and reliability of these reports are critical for medico-legal processes. This study assesses the diagnostic precision and concordance of forensic reports issued by CHCs and FHCs compared to advanced forensic medical evaluations (Sunay & Serpil, 2004).

Materials and Methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted on 41 cases referred to the Forensic Medicine Clinic at Ordu University Training and Research Hospital between January 1, 2020, and December 31, 2024, following forensic evaluations at CHCs and FHCs. Demographic data, referral reasons, lesion classifications, and concordance with advanced forensic assessments were analyzed. The chi-square test was used for statistical comparisons ($p < 0.05$).

Results: Of the 41 cases, 48.8% ($n=20$) were female, and 51.2% ($n=21$) were male, with a mean age of 41.46 ± 21.55 years (females: 34.50 ± 18.90 years, males: 48.09 ± 22.25 years). The leading cause for forensic evaluation was physical assault (85.4%, $n=34$), followed by sharp/blunt instrument injuries (7.3%, $n=3$), falls (4.9%, $n=2$), and penetrating injuries (2.4%, $n=1$). Most cases were referred from FHCs (65.9%, $n=27$), while 34.1% ($n=14$) were from CHCs. 63.4% ($n=26$) of cases required referral to higher-level institutions, with 46.3% ($n=19$) needing advanced diagnostic and therapeutic interventions and 17.1% ($n=7$) requiring specialist evaluation ($p=0.44$). Lesion classification inconsistencies were significant: 34.1% ($n=14$) of CHC/FHC reports used "hyperemia", but 21.9% ($n=9$) of these were reclassified as "ecchymosis" upon forensic reevaluation. Cases initially documented as having no traumatic findings were 7.3% ($n=3$) in CHC/FHC reports, but this rate increased to 24.4% ($n=10$) after forensic examination. Among cases with suspected fractures (9.7%, $n=4$), radiological confirmation was found in 7.3% ($n=3$). Life-threatening injuries were identified in 4.87% ($n=2$), while 17.1% ($n=7$) required medical intervention beyond simple treatment.

Conclusion: Forensic reports from CHCs and FHCs show significant inconsistencies compared to advanced forensic evaluations, particularly in lesion classification, fracture detection, and identification of traumatic findings (Rizzo, 2024; Yavuz & Yavuz, 2006). The frequent use of vague terminology and diagnostic discrepancies highlight the need for more precise forensic documentation. Enhancing forensic training among primary care physicians could improve report accuracy, ensuring more reliable medico-legal assessments (Kuş, Avşar, & Karabekiroğlu, 2023).

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Forensic assessment, traumatic lesions, family medicine

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Melike Taskiran

Department of Forensic Medicine

Ordu University Training and Research Hospital

Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6324-9229>

dr.melikos86@gmail.com